

DESIGN FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLES FOR IMPROVED ORAL DELIVERY OF BCS CLASS II DRUG

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Abstract:

The discovery of new drug molecules often encounters low water solubility, limiting dissolution and oral bioavailability. Researchers face challenges in developing delivery systems for poorly soluble drugs. The Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) categorizes drugs by solubility and membrane penetration. BCS class II drugs, like griseofulvin, have low water solubility but high membrane permeability, resulting in poor oral bioavailability. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) are a promising solution, enhancing solubility by reducing particle size and increasing surface area. Griseofulvin, an anti-fungal BCS class II drug, was loaded into SLNs using hot homogenization, cold homogenization, and solvent-emulsification evaporation. Hot homogenization yielded the smallest particles (125-250 nm) and highest entrapment efficiency (70-90%) using glyceryl monostearate. Optimization via a 3³ factorial design examined surfactant concentration, drug-to-lipid ratio, and stabilizer concentration. Optimal conditions included 1% PVA, 4% Tween80, and a 1:5 drug-to-lipid ratio, achieving particle sizes below 200 nm. Higher stirring speeds (2000 rpm) and longer times (60 minutes) reduced particle size, while temperature variations (25-40°C) had minimal impact. Filtration improved particle uniformity by removing excess surface lipid. The optimized SLN batch (GMS-9) showed high entrapment efficiency (87.50%), drug loading (17.50%), yield (95.20%), small particle size (151.1 nm), low PDI (0.172), and stable zeta potential (-40.3 mV). In vitro release studies indicated extended griseofulvin release up to 24 hours (89.47%), compared to a 4-hour release (98.23%) from a drug suspension. Stability tests over six months at 5°C and 25°C showed minimal changes, confirming good stability. SLNs enhance the solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs like griseofulvin, offering an effective strategy for improving oral drug delivery.

Keywords: griseofulvin, glyceryl monostearate,

Introduction:

The drug included in BCS class II shows high membrane permeability but have low water solubility as well. A large number of existing drug compounds belongs to that category like griseofulvin, cyclosporine, and itraconazole. Therefore, increasing in the drug solvency is viewed as a compelling strategy for enhancing the oral bioavailability of BCS class II drugs. Numerous physicochemical characteristics of the drug influence the dissolution profile. The Noyes-Whitney equation explained various factors responsible for altering the solubilization behaviour of the formulation including surface area, diffusion coefficient, saturated solubility concentration, the quantity of drug dissolved and media for dissolution used. Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs) are a promising solution, enhancing solubility by reducing particle size and increasing surface area. Griseofulvin, an anti-fungal BCS class II drug, was loaded into SLNs using hot homogenization, cold homogenization, and solvent-emulsification evaporation. Hot homogenization yielded the smallest particles (125-250 nm) and highest entrapment efficiency (70-90%) using glyceryl monostearate.

MATERIALS:

The drug sample was procured from GSK Pharmaceuticals Limited, Mumbai. The lipid Glyceryl monostearate (GMS), PVA (Poly vinyl alcohol) as a stabilizer and surfactant Tween 80 were purchased from SD fine chemicals Limited, Mumbai.

METHODOLOGY:

Preformulation studies:

Identification of drug using Ultra-violet Visible (UV) spectroscopy:

An UV spectra of griseofulvin was recorded using drug solution in methyl alcohol in a concentration of 10 µg/mL. The wave length of UV analysis was in the range of 200- 400 nm at normal room temperature

Identification of drug and Drug excipient compatibility by FTIR studies

FTIR is one the most promising method for drug identification and polymerinteraction studies of sample compounds. Here in this technology, potassium bromide (KBr) pellets were formed by mixing a small quantity of drug and drug with excipients. The spectra using FTIR spectrophotometer was recorded in a transmittance mode ranging 4000to 400cm⁻¹wavelength.

Freeze Drying Process for preparation of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

The prepared solid lipid nanoparticles were subjected to lyophilization using a freeze dryer. Lyophilization is done to improve the physical stability of developed solid lipid nanoparticles. The lyophilization process required cryoprotective agents before running the process to avoid

aggregation of lipid nanoparticles during freeze drying. Mannitol and sucrose were chosen as cryoprotectants for lyophilization. 5% and 10% concentration of both the cryoprotectant were examined. Initially, the samples were freeze dried at -40°C and subsequently temperature was increased up to 25°C at the increasing rate of 5°C per hour. The product obtained after freeze drying were processed by sonicator for 2 minutes

Determination of entrapment efficiency and drug loading

Entrapment efficiency is the study of drug amount that is encapsulated in the lipid matrix and quantity of drug present in supernatant layer received after the process of centrifugation at very high speed of 16000 rpm for half an hour. The entrapment efficiency is the ratio of actual amount of drug loaded and theoretical amount of drug loaded in lipid nanoparticles. The loading of drug can be measured by subtracting the free drug amount from the total quantity of drug used in the formulation. The entrapment efficiency and drug loading can be calculated using the formulas given below²³⁵:

$$\%EE = \text{free drug amount} / \text{total weight of drug} * 100$$

$$\% \text{ Drug loading} = \text{drug entrapped in SLNs} / \text{weight of vehicle} * 100$$

Determination of yield of SLNs

Yield of the formulation indicates the quantity of solid lipid nanoparticles achieved after the preparation. The yield is derived from gravimetric analysis. In this process a 10 mL suspension of drug was dried until the weight was constant to express the ratio of lipid present after drying and used initially. The yield was calculated in percentage.

Analysis of particle size distribution

The particle analysis in solid lipid nanoparticles was investigated by photon correlation spectroscopy method. For this study, the dispersion of solid lipid nanoparticles was diluted with purified water in 1:2 ratios and final dispersion was filtered using membrane filter of $0.45\mu\text{m}$. The angle for light scattering study was fixed at 90°C . The study was carried out at room temperature (25°C). Three reading were taken for calculating average mean to avoid any errors.

Determination of zeta potential

The zeta potential studies for prepared formulations were carried out utilizing Zeta sizer instrument. For the preparation of sample, the drug loaded solid lipid nanoparticles were diluted with purified water in the ratio of 1:2. The sample were analysed three times and average mean was taken into consideration.

Surface study by Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was utilized to evaluate surface characteristics of developed solid lipid nanoparticles. The prepared SLNs dispersion was first diluted with purified water in the ratio of 1:100. The diluted dispersion was filtered through membrane filter of 0.45 μm . The filtered sample was kept on a copper grid coated with carbon. The sample was put on the dried grid mixed with diluted solution of phospho-tungstic acid. The slide was fixed by a cover slip and observed under light microscope.

Surface morphological studies by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) The surface morphology is useful for study 3D structure of a particles. The study was performed using scanning electron microscopy. The sample was fixed and dehydrated with acetone. After drying, the sample was coated with gold for imaging. The SEM was performed at 25°C.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) study

X-Ray diffraction is the measurement of diffraction angle and spacing of lattice in the crystalline sample. These diffracted X-Rays were detected and counted. The study was investigated using Panalytical XpertPro Diffractometer. The sample of drug loaded solid lipid nanoparticles were analyzed.

DSC analysis of sample

DSC is a thermal analysis to measure the amount of heat required to increase the temperature of processed sample. This study was performed using DSC instrument. The sample of pure drug, lipid and drug loaded SLNs were analyzed in the temperature range of 0-300°C.

Investigation of In-Vitro Dissolution

In-vitro dissolution studies were performed using membrane dialysis method. The dialysis membrane was made of cellulose. It was treated with specific treatment before performing dissolution studies.

STABILITY TESTING:

The griseofulvin loaded SLNs were poured in 10 ml ampoule and sealed. The sealed ampoules were kept at temperature exposure of 5°C and 25°C for a time period of 6 months to evaluate stability of developed formulation. The particles were analyzed for changes in particle size, zeta potential and entrapment efficiency during the studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Identification of drug by UV spectrophotometer.

Fig 1: UV-scan for griseofulvin in methanol

Physical Characteristic of Griseofulvin

Physical form	:	Crystalline solid
Colour	:	White
Odour	:	Odourless
Melting point	:	221°C
Solubility	:	Less soluble in acetone, benzene, soluble in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, solubility increases in hot solvents and practically insoluble in purified water.

Fig 2: Calibration plot of griseofulvin in methanol

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Fig.3 ftri studies of pure drug.

Fig. 4Effect of RPM on Particle size

Fig 5 Effect of Time on Particle size

Fig. 6 Effect of Temperature on Particle size

Fig 7 effect of time on Particle size

Fig. 8 Effect of Filtration on Particle size

Table 1: % Entrapment efficiency, % drug loading and % yield for optimized Formulation (n=3)

Optimized formulation	Entrapment efficiency	Drug loading	% Yield
GF-SLNs (GMS-9)	87.5 ±2.19	17.50 ±0.43	95.20 ±2.3

Table 2: Particle size, PDI and zeta potential of optimized formulation (n=3)

Optimized formulation	Particle size(nm)	Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Zeta potential(mV)
GF-SLN(GMS-9)	151.1±10.7	0.172 ±0.07	-40.3±0.8

Fig.9 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) image of GF-SLN

Fig. 10 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image of GF-SLN

Fig. 11 DSC Thermograms showing drug, lipid, blank SLN, GF-SLN

Fig.12 XRD pattern showing drug, lipid and GF-SLN

Fig.13 In-vitro release pattern showing release profile of pure drugsuspension and griseofulvin loaded SLNs

Conclusion:

The current research proved that solid lipid nanoparticles is a adaptable technology that have a potential ability to enhance the solubility of poorly water soluble drug listed in BCS class II drug. The griseofulvin is a lipophilic drug which oral bioavailability is limited due to poor aqueous solubility. Solid lipid nanoparticles are the nano lipid carriers which encapsulate the lipophilic drug in the lipid matrix. The SLN approach was utilized to increase the solubility and oral bioavailability of griseofulvin. The solid lipid nanoparticles containing griseofulvin were prepared by hot homogenization method after method optimization. The glyceryl monostearate was used as a lipid, tween 80 as a surfactant and PVA as a stabilizer in the formulation. The prepared formulation batches were analyzed for particle size, poly dispersity index, drug entrapment efficiency, drug loading, zeta potential and yield. Drug lipid ratio was selected as 1:5, surfactant concentration 4% and stabilizer concentration 1% after optimization of formulation variables. The optimized batch of GF-SLNs was found to be stable in accelerated stability studies at room temperature. The in-vitro release studies showed the extended release of drug from drug loaded SLNs in 24 hrs of studies.

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